

Supplement A.

Table A1. Reducing pollution concentration in rain gardens (and experimental laboratory column)

Pollutant	Removal [%]	Country	Reference
TN	74	Korea	[1]
	56.84	China	[2]
	(-52)–89	USA	[3]
	-1.7	China	[4]
	41, 82, and 53	China	[5]
	33, 50, 78, and 92	Sweden	[6]
	26.7-46.9	China	[7]
TKN	31.7	USA	[3]
	68 and 75	USA	[8]
	1.6	Canada	[9]
NO ₃ -N	49.84	China	[2]
	24	USA	[8]
	42-63 and 29-39	USA	[10]
	65.5	USA	[11]
	4.8	China	[4]
	9	USA	[12]
	1, 33, and 84	China	[5]
TP	74	Korea	[1]
	56.99	China	[2]
	71 and 81	USA	[8]
	-65.6	Canada	[9]
	21.6	China	[4]
	81.7	USA	[13]
	87.3	USA	[14]
	70	USA	[12]
	26.5-59.0	China	[7]
TSS	85	Korea	[1]
	51.79	China	[2]
	74.5	Canada	[9]
	68.3	China	[4]
	90	New Zealand	[15]
	96	USA	[12]
	70	USA	[16]
	31.2-47.9	China	[7]
	83	USA	[17]
Cu	92 and 98	USA	[8]
	-14.1	Canada	[9]
	37.8	New Zealand	[15]
	56.4 and 88.9	New Zealand	[18]
	72	USA	[19]
	63	Norway	[20]
	68	USA	[21]
	-9	USA	[16]
82.4 and 92.4	USA	[22]	
Zn	97 and 98	USA	[8]

Pollutant	Removal [%]	Country	Reference
	48.3	Canada	[9]
	95.6	New Zealand	[15]
	73.5 and 83.2	New Zealand	[18]
	99	USA	[19]
	93	Norway	[20]
	83	USA	[16]
	97.7 and 98.7	USA	[22]
COD	91	Korea	[1]
	39.8	China	[2]
	-50.6	Canada	[9]
	-13	China	[4]
	27.1-51.7	China	[7]
PAH	100	Canada	[9]
	98	USA	[17]
	95	USA	[19]
	84-100	USA	[23]
HOI	100	Canada	[9]
	98	USA	[12]
	80	USA	[24]
	78-93	USA	[25]

Table A2. Reducing pollution concentration in bioretention cells (and experimental laboratory column)

Pollutant	Removal [%]	Country	Reference
TN	41, 82, and 53	China	[5]
	33, 50, 78, and 92	Sweden	[6]
	26.7-46.9	China	[7]
	20	USA	[26]
	59 and 90	USA	[27]
	32.2	USA	[28]
	50 and 67	China	[29]
	35	USA	[30]
	54	USA	[31]
TKN	68 and 75	USA	[8]
	22.1	USA	[26]
	44.4	USA	[28]
	44	USA	[30]
	49 and 59	USA	[31]
	65	USA	[32]
NO ₃ -N	1, 33, and 84	China	[5]
	24	USA	[8]
	9	USA	[12]
	31.4	Mexico	[33]
TP	26.5-59	China	[7]
	71 and 81	USA	[8]
	70	USA	[12]

Pollutant	Removal [%]	Country	Reference
	81.7	USA	[13]
	21.9	USA	[26]
	31.6	USA	[28]
	51 and 92	China	[29]
	62	USA	[30]
	58 and 63	USA	[31]
	83	USA	[32]
TSS	31.2-47.9	China	[7]
	96	USA	[12]
	70	USA	[16]
	83	USA	[17]
	69.4	USA	[26]
	59.6	USA	[28]
	83 and 85	China	[29]
	94	USA	[30]
	96	USA	[32]
	92.6	Mexico	[33]
	61	USA	[34]
Cu	92 and 98	USA	[8]
	-9	USA	[16]
	72	USA	[19]
	82.4 and 92.4	USA	[22]
	54	USA	[28]
	28	USA	[30]
	81	USA	[35]
Zn	97 and 98	USA	[8]
	83	USA	[16]
	99	USA	[19]
	97.7 and 98.7	USA	[22]
	77	USA	[28]
	74	USA	[30]
	79	USA	[35]
COD	27.1-51.7	China	[7]
	51 and 65	China	[29]
	41.9	Mexico	[33]
PAH	98	USA	[17]
	95	USA	[19]
	84-100	USA	[23]
	90	USA	[34]
HOI	98	USA	[12]
	80	USA	[24]
	78-93	USA	[25]

Table A2. Reducing pollution concentration in bioswales

Pollutant	Removal [%]	Country	Reference
TN	61.37 and 76	China	[2]
	5.1	USA	[36]
	43.6	USA	[37]
	12.9	China	[38]
TKN	23.4	China	[38]
	7.9	USA	[36]
	41.7	USA	[37]
	-52.2 and -30.9	France	[39]
NO ₃ -N	61.06 and 78.54	China	[2]
	0.2	USA	[36]
	44.9	USA	[37]
	-8	China	[38]
TP	61.06 and 78.54	China	[2]
	6.3	USA	[36]
	48.3	USA	[37]
	-72	China	[38]
	-55.6 and -86.1	France	[39]
	20-23	Australia	[40]
TSS	72.66 and 88.16	China	[2]
	45	USA	[36]
	81.8	USA	[37]
	-14.1 and 38.6	France	[39]
	50-80	Australia	[40]
	80.8	USA	[41]
Cu	79.4	USA	[37]
	39.5	China	[38]
	18.2 and 51.5	France	[39]
	69	USA	[41]
	77 and 88	USA	[42]
Zn	87.5	USA	[37]
	54.9	China	[38]
	85	USA	[41]
	-36.1 and 45.4	France	[39]
	77 and 88	USA	[42]
	70 and 79	France	[43]
COD	64.87 and 85.34	China	[2]
	13.7	China	[38]
	-40.8 and 14.2	France	[39]
PAH	-27.7 and 27.7	France	[39]
	82.1	USA	[41]
	96.2	France	[43]
	90	France	[44]
HOI	58 and 69	UK	[45]

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